

EMPYREAL AND PIEZOELECTRIC DEPENDED POWER ORIGINATION STRUCTURE

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Abstract: In topical years we are fronting the power cut problems, increasing mandate of electricity, etc due to the development of industrial automation systems that requires huge power. To overcome this requirement, we can use the renewable sources of energy to generate electricity. Solar energy is a renewable source of energy that has been with use since the inception of life. This heliacal energy is arrested through the solar panels and then it is converted to solar electricity using Photovoltaic (PV) technology. In addition to this Piezoelectric Energy Harvesting is also done by using piezoelectric effect. In this paper, piezoelectric established energy reaping technology is applied to produce electrical energy from mechanical stress (vibrations). Piezoelectric material is used to harvest vibration energy from humans walking, machinery vibrating, automobiles moving on a roadway, etc. Since movement is everywhere, the ability to seizure this energy cheaply would be a significant progression towards greater efficiency and cleaner energy production. This paper implements a competent way to electrify or generate electricity using solar power and piezoelectric energy harvesting circuit and stock it in a battery. This electricity is used to charge the electric vehicles in one spot and all the electronic gadgets in another spot.

Key Words: Heliacal energy, piezoelectric effect, Battery, Electric vehicles, Electronic gadgets.

I. Introduction: With growing apprehension of global warming and the exhaustion of

fossil fuel reserves, several are beholding at sustainable energy solution to preserve the earth for the future generations. Other than hydro power, vibration and empyreal(solar) energy embraces the maximum potential to encounter our energy demands. The vibration energy is capable of providing great volume of power but its presence is highly indeterminate as it can be here one moment and gone in another. In the same way, stellar energy is existing throughout the day nevertheless the solar irradiation levels differ owing to sun intensity and impulsive shadows cast by clouds, birds, trees, etc. The common inherent drawbacks of vibration and photovoltaic systems are their intermittent natures that make them unreliable. However, by combining these two intermittent sources and incorporating maximum power point tracking (MPPT) algorithm, the system's power transfer efficiency and reliability can be enhanced significantly. When a source is inadequate, the load demands some other energy sources to compensate for the alteration. In such case Solar energy is a renewable source of energy that has been with use since the inception of life. This heliacal energy is arrested through the solar panels and then it is converted to solar electricity using Photovoltaic (PV) technology and collect it in a battery.

Figure 1.1
Solar tracking and storage

Owing to improvement in the field of technology in recent years, wireless data transmission techniques are frequently used in electronic devices. For driving them we depend on power supply through cables, else power may be supplied from batteries. But while drifting for longer distances endlessly we may not be able to find power supply for these devices to activate or to boost their batteries. So, in order to operate them endlessly we need a power source that provides nonstop energy to activate these devices. The mechanical vibrations which are produced by the automobiles can be used as a basis of energy for producing electrical energy that can be applied to the electronic equipment to operate. These vibrations are produced by different vehicles everywhere which are going as a waste.

Figure 1.2 Piezoelectric Effect

Piezoelectric materials are used by this technique, where distortions done by the vibrations are directly converted into the electrical charge via piezoelectric effect and principle of electromagnetic induction

between coil and magnetic field that produces Electromotive force (EMF) in the coil and so it provides movement to the performance magnet by the vibrations. All the piezoelectric materials and magnets are used as the energy renovation devices for converting mechanical vibrations into electrical energy.

Figure 1.3 Generating Piezoelectric Effect

In this framework, we introduced two methods and considered its output performance provided input vibrations, by using piezoelectric materials and also generating solar power using solar panels.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW:

L.Mora, M. Deakin, and A. Reid, "Strategic principles for smart city development: A multiple case study analysis of European best practices," Technol. Forecast. Soc. Change, no. July, pp. 0–1, 2018.

The absence of urban physical space and stable development of the energy matrix, allow us to visualize the future where the stable improvement of the existing matrix, becomes a vital practice towards more intellectual and self-sustainable cities. By using Priya and Inman's solution, we follow their piezo electric solution to come out of this energy crisis. Their quote states that: "One of the probable solutions to this energy crisis are energy harvesting techniques, which allow assortment of residual energy from environmental sources, clean and free."

However, this is a challenge, since generating new possibilities to satisfy the rising energy needs, leads to an essential growth in Research and Development of such power generation support.

M. Shariz Ansari¹, Rajat Jaiswal², Mihir², Pushpa Singh Patel² Assistant Professor, Dept. of EN, KIET Group of Institution, Ghaziabad, India¹ “Solar Photovoltaic Power Generation with Automatic Tracking System” International Journal of Advanced Research in Electrical, Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering IJAREEIE 2320 – 3765 Volume 6, Issue 5 MAY 2017

The core objective of this project is to develop a programmed solar tracking structure where the solar panels will be aligned with the Sunlight in order to make best use of solar power. The system concentrates on the controller design where it allows the system to track the extreme intensity of Sunlight hits the solar panel. When the strength of Sunlight is reducing, this structure mechanically changes its direction to get extreme intensity of Sunlight. LDR light detector sensor is used to trace the coordinates of the Sunlight by spotting illumination level of the Sunlight. To adjust the appropriate position of the panel, a DC-gear motor is used. Here the microcontroller acts as a main processor. This project is designed for low power and suburban usage applications. The hardware testing reveals that the system is able to track and trail the Sunbeams concentration in order to get maximum solar power as output.

III. EXISTING SYSTEM:

Energy Floors is a company located in Rotterdam and was built in 2008, The Netherlands. The company practices two methods to produce electricity; one is to transfer the kinetic energy into electric energy, and the other one is to use power-generating heliacal panels. Both the systems

are mounted on a walkable tile. The produced electrical energy is used to power lighting and USB devices. Each tile can produce between 5-20 Watt per step.

A study was conducted in the Republic of Korea, in 2019 in which the electrical engineering students proposed an automatic cell phone charging system that extracts clean energy from cars passing on a speed bump. The projected combined segment uses 40 Piezoelectric generators that were mounted in the middle of a speed bump. The ending module was linked to a load resistance of 2k and produced an output power of 4086 mW at maximum.

Another proposed study is developed by the graduate students and doctors in China. They designed a structure that uses a combination of triboelectric, piezoelectric and electromagnetic approaches to generate power. Their proposed system produces electricity whenever a car passes over the device. Furthermore, the system has a wireless transmitter that sends all the information about the power generation to a designated computer.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM:

This paper proposes “**The empyreal and piezoelectric depended power origination structure**”. Here the power which is generated using the above mentioned two intermittent sources is stored in a battery and as a result this power is used to charge the electric vehicles in one spot and electronic gadgets in another spot. This concept mainly focuses on maximum power point algorithm (MPPT). The entire working of the circuit is controlled by the ARDUINO UNO microcontroller. This maximum power point is achieved by using LDR sensor. This Light Dependent Resistor is used to trace the coordinates of the sunlight and spotting the brightness level of the sunlight. To adjust the solar panel according to the illumination level of sunlight, a DC-gear motor is used.

This DC geared motor is controlled by L293D motor driver. In addition to this Piezoelectric Energy Harvesting is also done by using piezoelectric effect. In this paper, piezoelectric established energy reaping technology is applied to produce electrical energy from mechanical stress (vibrations). Piezoelectric material is used to harvest vibration energy from humans walking, machinery vibrating, automobiles moving on a roadway, etc. The collected voltage using both the sources which is stored in the battery is continuously measured by using voltage sensor and these values are displayed in the Liquid Crystal Display in a timely manner. As a result, this stored power is used to charge the electric vehicles and electronic gadgets in two separate spots.

V. BLOCK DIAGRAM:

The block diagram of the proposed structure is shown in the below fig. The LDR sensor used to trace the maximum brightness level of the sunlight and the dc geared motor is used to adjust the position of the solar panel to gain the maximum energy from sunlight. The piezo electric material circuit is designed to generate the electricity from human and vehicle vibrations. The voltage produced by the solar panel and piezoelectric circuit is commonly connected to the battery. The Voltage sensor is used to measure the collected voltage in a battery and these voltage values are displayed on an LCD.

The power stored in the battery is used by two charging stations one is electric vehicle charging spot and the other one is electronic gadget charging spot.

VI. MODULE DESCRIPTION:

Arduino UNO:

Arduino Uno is a microcontroller board constructed on the ATmega328 processor. The controller contains 14 digital input/output pins. Out of 14 pins, 6 can be used for Pulse Width Modulated outputs and 6 can be used as analog inputs. It also includes USB connection, Power jack and a Reset button. The specifications of Arduino UNO make it an excellent choice for projects of all kinds.

Solar Panel:

Solar energy initiates with the sun. Solar panels are also known as "PV panels" which are used to convert light from the sun, which is collection of particles of energy called "photons", into electricity that can be used to power electrical loads. The Solar electricity can be used for an extensive variety of applications such as remote power systems, telecommunications kit, remote sensing, and also to generate electricity by residential and commercial solar electric systems.

Piezoelectric Sensor:

A sensor which works on the principle of piezoelectricity is acknowledged as a piezoelectric sensor. It is a phenomenon where electrical energy is engendered when a mechanical pressure is applied to a material. They have been effectively used in numerous

This paper comes up with an awareness of using vibration and solar energy combined for producing electricity for our impending needs. This efficient power generation system is of low maintenance and less expensive. To get extreme efficiency this kind of systems should be fixed in demanding crowd places such as railway stations, malls, bus stops and footpaths, speed breaker, highway, etc. in future we will also be able to add other power generation systems to rise competence in order to increase the output power.

IX. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have examined and detected the practicability of applying piezoelectricity for converting the mechanical vibrations of roadway to generate useful electricity. We have also examined the feasibility of using solar concentrators to improve the output power of the solar panel to a significant level. This concept helps to implement the power generation system within the budget and thereby reducing pressure on conventional power use and current generation.

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